

The Influence of Transformational Leadership of Commissioned Police Officers and Ethical Climate on Job Satisfaction of Non-Commissioned Police Officers in Agusan Del Sur

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Abstract:- The study determined the influence of transformational leadership of commissioned police officers and ethical climate on job satisfaction of non-commissioned police officers in Agusan del Sur, Philippines. A non-experimental quantitative research design using the descriptive-correlational technique, Pearson r and was applied to 300 randomly selected non-commissioned officers as respondents of the study using modified survey questionnaire. Results showed very high levels of transformational leadership, ethical climate, and job satisfaction among non-commissioned officers. Significant relationships were shown between transformational leadership and job satisfaction, and between ethical climate and job satisfaction. Further, Transformational leadership and ethical climate revealed a combined significant effect on job satisfaction among non-commissioned police officers.

Keywords:- criminal justice, commissioned police officers, non-commissioned police officers, transformational leadership, ethical climate, Philippines.

I. INTRODUCTION

There is a high probability of discontent in the profession, and this unhappiness may have a detrimental effect on an individual's quality of work life as well as their psychosocial (Songcog, & Guhao, Jr, 2020). Job satisfaction, organizational dedication to obtain a competitive edge and important employee retention are all factors to consider (Fatt, Khin, & Heng, 2010). Every employee deals with work overload, workplace stress, and personal life stress, this, has an impact on their productivity and job satisfaction (Syed, 2011).

Employee satisfaction is undeniably important in the face of the dynamic and ever-increasing challenges of sustaining the organization's efficiency (Oswald, Proto, & Sgroi, 2015). The most significant factors contributing to job satisfaction are pay, work performance, fringe supervision, and co-worker relationships (Islam & Saha, 2016). The nature of the job and sentiments of job satisfaction, as well as connections with superiors and peers, are all relevant to the difficulties that each organization faces. Large consumer expectations, for example, may put pressure on employers, driving staff to become more competitive within the firm. The workplace's pressures and different needs present a leadership challenge

that puts people in difficult positions (Bakotic & Babic, 2013).

Leadership is viewed as critical in the beginning and implementation of organizational transformations (Coetsier, 1997). They need to animate their devotees' endeavors and pay unmistakable regard for each and every individual supporter's requirement for improvement. Most past investigations affirmed that these qualities are fundamentally identified with representatives of job satisfaction (Heng, Kowang, Long & Yusof, 2014). Non-commissioned officers reported higher levels of happiness in their work lives as a direct result of the idealized influence that had a major and positive influence on central objectives (Clarke, 2018).

Moreover, antisocial conduct has been labeled as a term for negative workplace behavior (Robinson & O'Leary-Kelly, 1998). Ethical climate has provided helpful insight into the importance of ethical climate in organizations and how it influences employees' attitudes and behavior, but it has been limited in a number of ways (Shin, 2012). The data showed that there is a connection between the ethical atmosphere of the company and many other characteristics of employee happiness in their positions. This means that a positive ethical climate in the workplace will enhance employee dedication and job satisfaction (Okpara & Wynn, 2008)

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The participants of the study will be the non-commissioned police personnel in the province of Agusan del Sur. This study excludes police officers who newly augmented in police stations, those under field training program and those non-commissioned police officers assigned outside the Agusan del Sur. For the convenience of finding respondents who were available right away, they should withdraw the concept of voluntary engagement if they are uncomfortable answering the inquiry. This means that the universal sample will be utilized for this study which will include three hundred (300) Police Non-commission police officers in the Province of Agusan del Sur.

The main draft of the research instrument will be submitted to the research adviser for remarks, proposals and suggestions to improve its presentation with the remedies to be incorporated and coordinated. The last duplicates will be submitted to panel of experts for refinement. The last amendment will be made by fusing the rectifications, remarks and recommendations given by the expert validators before the gathering of data. Prior to the administration of the polls, they were guided to 40 respondents and the dependability of the items was computed whose result shows a generally Cronbach's Alpha of 0.886 or high reliability. With the endorsement of the research adviser, the surveys were directed to the recognized respondents of the study.

In the collecting of data, the analyst will ask consent from the Provincial Director PCOL Ringo C. Zarzoso, requesting his thoughtful endorsement. Following the endorsement of the Provincial Director, the researcher will ask permission to the Provincial Director to disseminate the research instrument to all municipal station to 300 police officers. It was conducted July 13, 2021 and finished on July 20, 2021. Upon the endorsement, the researcher will actually visit each municipality to orient police officer respondents about the reason and meaning of the study. The researcher will by and by disseminate and direct the research instrument on transformational leadership, ethical climate and job satisfaction of the Non- commission Police Officer to guarantee 100% recovery of the survey. At that point, a documentation will be gotten from each Municipal Station that the researcher really gathered the data from the respondents of the study. Thusly, the information that assembled will be counted, arranged, investigated and deciphered genuinely.

The following scales were used to evaluate the degree of transformational leadership of the respondents:

Rating Scale	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
4.20 - 5.00	Very High	Transformational leadership is always felt.
3.40 - 4.19	High	Transformational leadership is often felt.
2.30 – 3.39	Moderate	Transformational leadership is sometimes felt.
1.80 – 2.29	Low	Transformational leadership is seldom felt.
1.00 – 1.79	Very Low	Transformational leadership is never felt.

The second independent variable, ethical climate, was measured utilizing questions adapted from (Bronson, Cullen & Victor, 1993) It contained seven indicators namely: conscience, organization competence in getting rich, purpose of the company, societal obligation, moral fortitude, and adherence to norms and regulations. Participants were provided with these responses:

Rating Scale	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
4.20 - 5.00	Very High	This means that ethical climate is always manifested.
3.40 - 4.19	High	This means that ethical climate is often manifested.
2.30 – 3.39	Moderate	This means that ethical climate is sometimes manifested.
1.80 – 2.29	Low	This means that ethical climate is seldom manifested.
1.00 – 1.79	Very Low	This means that ethical climate is never manifested.

The dependent variable, job satisfaction, was measured utilizing questions adapted from (Bagiatis & Koustelios, 1997). It contained six indicators namely: Working condition, Supervision, Pay, Job itself, Organization as a whole and Promotion. Participants were provided with these responses:

This study will be conducted in Police Regional Office 13, Agusan del Sur Police Provincial Office Camp DO Plaza, Patin-ay, Prosperidad, Agusan del Sur. The headquarter represent the 13 municipalities and 1 city of the province, these are: Bayugan City, Bunawan, Esperanza, La Paz, Loreto, Prosperidad, Rosario, San Francisco, San Luis, Santa Josefa, Sibagat, Talacogon, Trento and Veruela.

This study used three survey questionnaires to gather the data. The survey is useful instrument for assessing huge populaces which gave near simplicity and testing connections between two or more variables. Determination of a research approach relies upon various components, including the reason for the research, the kind of examination inquiries to be replied, and the accessibility of assets (Ponto, 2015). The researcher used downloaded and modified survey questionnaire as essential instrument in gathering the required information from the respondents. The said survey instrument in Cronbach-alpha test score featured three parts involving the variable under study: transformational leadership, ethical climate and job satisfaction. Cronbach's alpha (CA) was utilized in study approval interaction to decide the interior consistency of overview addresses that heap in similar variables.

The first independent variable, transformational leadership, was measured utilizing questions adapted from (Campbell, 2011) It contained seven indicators namely: Individualized consideration, Encourage the heart, Inspirational motivation, Intellectual stimulation, Challenge the process, make it possible for others to function as models for you. The following replies been made available to the respondents:

Rating Scale	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
4.20 - 5.00	Very High	This means that job satisfaction is always manifested.
3.40 - 4.19	High	This means that job satisfaction is often manifested.
2.30 – 3.39	Moderate	This means that job satisfaction is sometimes manifested.
1.80 – 2.29	Low	This means that job satisfaction is seldom manifested.
1.00 – 1.79	Very Low	This means that job satisfaction is never manifested.

This research utilized quantitative, enlightening correlation design as the most suitable contemplating the explanation and issue clarification. A decent portrayal is critical to exactly depict the association between dependent variable and independent variables. According to Hall & Quick, (2015). Quantitative exploration is frequently thought of as more 'logical' than the subjective approach. This strategy is more legitimate on the grounds that it utilizes the study in gathering information from a wide scope of elements by choosing a delegate test of a colossal populace. Moreover, relationship is utilized to research and gauge the association between at least two variables. Also, the essential information was produced through adjusted study instruments.

Considering quantitative research plans are regularly used to take a gander at easy going relationship, however they can likewise be utilized to take a gander at affiliation and connection between factors (Baker, 2017). One may not be discerning of the association of the factors, or may assume that a variable is influenced by the other.

However, the independent variable isn't controlled in correlational examinations, consequently the end that the variable's relationship to one another is causative with only connection as the premise. Generally, the research design ends up being reasonable in inspecting the connection between the factors, transformational leadership, ethical climate and job satisfaction of police officers in Agusan del Sur.

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A. Transformational Leadership

The amount of transformative leadership shown by the officers is demonstrated in Table 1, in Agusan del Sur. The overall mean score is 4.39 with a standard deviation of 0.43, and described as very high which means the transformational leadership was always observed by the police officers. Further, result showed that police officer manifest very high transformational leadership.

Further, the mean scores of the indicators of transformational leadership are revealed as follows: Model the Way 4.48 or very high with a standard deviation of 0.465; Inspirational Motivation a mean score of 4.43 or very high with a standard deviation of 0.475; Encourage the Heart a mean score of 4.41 or very high with a standard deviation of 0.592; Individualized Consideration a mean score of 4.41 or very high with a standard deviation of 0.479; and Enable Others to Act a mean score of 4.32 or very high with a standard deviation of 0.538;

The very high level of transformational leadership was because of the extremely high marks of the respondents in terms of: Individualized Consideration, Encourage the Heart, Inspirational Motivation, Enable Others to Act and Model the Way. Putting their trust on their people and provide leadership involving active listening towards their people.

The result was congruent statement of Sitzmann & Yeo, (2013). Transformative leadership results create each team participant their full focus, make an effort to comprehend their requirements by actively listening to them, and offer moral comfort if team members are feeling irritated on the job. The employees' perceptions of their own security are improved as a result of these supporting actions, and they are encouraged to show the version of themselves that is most effective while conducting this project.

Indicators	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Individualized Consideration	0.479	4.41	Very High
Encourage the Heart	0.592	4.31	Very High
Inspirational Motivation	0.475	4.43	Very High
Enable others to act	0.538	4.32	Very High
Model the way	0.465	4.48	Very High
Overall	0.432	4.39	Very High

Table 1: The level of Transformational Leadership

B. Ethical Climate

Depicted in Table 2 is the level of Ethical Climate of Non-Commissioned Police Officers in Agusan del Sur. The overall mean rating is 4.28 with a standard deviation of 0.43 as very high which meant that ethical climate was oftentimes observed by the police officers in Agusan del Sur. Also, this indicate that police officers had very high level of Ethical Climate.

Further, the mean scores of the indicators of ethical climate are identified to be the aforementioned: Professional Codes with a mean score of 4.38 or very high with a standard deviation of 0.544; Social Responsibility with a mean score of 4.37 or very high with a standard deviation of 0.574; Team Interest with a mean score of 4.32 or very high with a standard deviation of 0.501; Organization Profit efficiency with a mean score of 4.26 or very high probable error of

0.561; Rules with a mean score of 4.26 or very high with a standard deviation of 0.542; Personal Morality with a mean score of 4.26 or very high probable error of 0.626; and Self-Interest gained a mean score of 4.12 or high probable error of 0.549.

The very high level of ethical climate was because of the extremely high marks of the respondents in terms of: Professional Codes, Social Responsibility, Team Interest, Organization Profit efficiency, Rules, Personal Morality except self-interest. This means that efficient solutions to problems are always sought and people are very concerned about what is generally best for police officer in the organization. Therefore, the most important consideration in

their organization is each person’s sense of right and wrong and in their organization, everyone is expected to stick by organization rules and procedures.

The results are consistent with those of Elias's research (2021), which found that even being excellent mechanism doing things correctly, while being appropriate method doing the proper way, and the individuals who are the most necessary work on the increased jobs. The result was supported with the statement of Cullen & Victor, (1988) a good ethical atmosphere is characterized by a collection of overt and covert views of processes and rules that are held in common by employees and contribute to the formation of norms for ethics code.

Indicators	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Self Interest	0.549	4.12	High
Organization Profit Efficiency	0.561	4.26	Very High
Team Interest	0.501	4.32	Very High
Social Responsibility	0.574	4.37	Very High
Personal Morality	0.626	4.26	Very High
Rules	0.542	4.26	Very High
Professional Codes	0.544	4.38	Very High
Overall	0.433	4.28	Very High

Table 2: The Level of Ethical Climate

C. Job Satisfaction

Illustrated in Table 3 is the level of Job Satisfaction of Non-Commissioned Police Officers in Agusan del Sur. The entire combined values were 4.28 with a predicted error of 0.43, which was classified as extremely high. This indicated that the police officers were quite satisfied with their jobs and did not experience any burnout. This also implied that job satisfaction of the police officers in Agusan del Sur is very high.

Further, the actually imply ratings of the several measures of occupational contentment were unveiled as follows: Pay with a mean score of 4.41 or very high predictable error of 0.626; Promotion with a mean score of 4.32 or very high predictable error of 0.591; Job Itself with a mean score of 4.32 or very high probable error of 0.542; Organizational as a Whole with a mean score of 4.26 or very high probable error of 0.594; Supervisors with a mean score of 4.21 or very high range of error of 0.584; and Working Condition 4.16 or high range of error of 0.581.

The extremely considerable degree of contentment with one's work was because of the extremely high marks of the respondents in terms of: Supervisor, Pay, Job Itself, Organization as a Whole and Promotion except Working Condition. Commissioned officers are constantly motivating their subordinates to work effectively by motivating people through coaching and commissioned officers are trusting their subordinates in the workplace.

The findings of the study is aligned with the contention of Enbom, Gustafsson, and Larson (2006) that work teams can be motivated though coaching..Similarly, the results is parallel to the study of Brower, Lester, Korsgaard, and Dineen (2009). Additionally, Abuhashesh, Al-Dmour & Masa'deh, (2019) stated that an individual has achieved something significant and is successful as a result of the effort that they put into their coworkers is one definition of job characteristics.

Indicators	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Working Condition	0.581	4.16	High
Supervisor	0.584	4.21	Very High
Pay	0.626	4.41	Very High
Job Itself	0.542	4.32	Very High
Organization as a whole	0.594	4.26	Very High
Promotion	0.591	4.32	Very High
Overall	0.436	4.28	Very High

Table 3: The Level of Job Satisfaction

D. Significance on the Relationship between the Transformational Leadership and Job Satisfaction

The findings of the analysis of the association between the independent component of idealized influence and the outcome variable of quality of work life are shown in Table 4. According to the findings, an organization culture had a

substantial positive relationship with job performance. as the overall r-value was .653 and p= 0.000 which is less than 0.05 level of significance. This means that Transformational Leadership is significantly linked with Job Satisfaction among Non-Commissioned Police Officers in Agusan del Sur. Thus, it was concluded that there is no

substantial association between innovative leadership on employee. This conclusion was reached.

Also, when the indicators of Transformational Leadership parallel with the indicators of Job satisfaction the following outcomes were obtained as a consequence. When Individualized Consideration was parallel with all indicators of Job Satisfaction yielded an overall $r = .513$ at $p < 0.000$ hence, significant; Encourage the Heart interconnected with view of all indicators of Job Satisfaction yielded an overall $r = .548$ $p < 0.000$ still, significant; Inspirational Motivation when interconnected with all indicators of Job Satisfaction yielded an overall $r = .555$ $p < 0.000$; Enable others to Act when associated with all indicators of Job Satisfaction yielded an overall $r = .564$ $p < 0.000$ also, significant; and Finally, Model the Way when associated with all indicators of Job Satisfaction yielded an overall $r = .590$ $p < 0.000$ likewise, significant.

The current study revealed that Job Satisfaction is significantly related to Transformational Leadership. The study is aligned with the study of Tesfaw, (2014) the discoveries demonstrated that a moderate, there is a link that may be described as both good and important between transformative leadership and work satisfaction. Result of the study is also parallel with the statement of Ahmad, Bushra, Naveed & U, (2011). The findings of the study concluded that transformational leadership positively affects job satisfaction and organizational commitment of employees. Subsequently, Independence in the industry grew as a direct result of leadership style, which in turn boosted work engagement. Happiness was associated with a reduction in the number of unfavorable occurrences (Boamah, Clarke, Laschinger & Wong, 2018).

Transformational Leadership	Job Satisfaction						
	Working Condition	Supervisor	Pay	Job Itself	Organization as a whole	Promotion	Overall
Individualized Consideration	.370* (0.000)	.321* (0.000)	.408* (0.000)	.369* (0.000)	.429* (0.000)	.389* (0.000)	.513* (0.000)
Encourage the Heart	.370* (0.000)	.325* (0.000)	.358* (0.000)	.447* (0.000)	.470* (0.000)	.476* (0.000)	.548* (0.000)
Inspirational Motivation	.319* (0.000)	.321* (0.000)	.485* (0.000)	.434* (0.000)	.460* (0.000)	.452* (0.000)	.555* (0.000)
Enable others to act	.415* (0.000)	.321* (0.000)	.401* (0.000)	.444* (0.000)	.485* (0.000)	.451* (0.000)	.564* (0.000)
Model the way	.331* (0.000)	.367* (0.000)	.467* (0.000)	.512* (0.000)	.517* (0.000)	.439* (0.000)	.590* (0.000)
Overall	.428* (0.000)	.389* (0.000)	.495* (0.000)	.521* (0.000)	.558* (0.000)	.523* (0.000)	.653* (0.000)

Table 4: Significance of the Relationship between the Transformational Leadership and Job Satisfaction

*Significant at 0.05 significance level.

The statistics about the degree of significant correlation between the two parameter Morality Attitude and the endogenous variable Work Motivation are shown in Table 5. According to the findings, an internal environment was shown to have a strong positive relationship with job performance as the overall r-value was .750 and $p < 0.000$ level of significance. This meant when Ethical Climate is very high; an increase of job satisfaction is also expected. Thus, there is a considerable connection among the ethical atmosphere and the level of pleasure one derives from their work.

Furthermore, the indicators of Ethical Climate linked with the indicators of Job Satisfaction yielded the following result. Self-interest with view of all indicators of job satisfaction yielded an overall $r = .565$ and $p < 0.000$ significant; Organizational Profit Efficiency .551 and $p < 0.000$ also, significant; Team interest .591 and $p < 0.000$ also, significant; Social Responsibility .597 and $p < 0.000$ still significant; Personal Morality .537 and $p < 0.000$ still significant; Rules .635 $p < 0.000$ thus, significant; and Finally, Professional Codes .617 and $p < 0.000$ also, significant. The

current study reveals a significant relationship between Ethical Climate and Job Satisfaction of police officers in Agusan del Sur. it only means that the police officers job satisfaction affects their ethical climate which is observed on this fact. In a singular state, indicators such as self-interest, organization profit efficiency, team interest, social responsibility and personal morality, rules and professional codes.

The result of the study is congruent to the study of Okpara & Wynn, (2008). There was a link between the ethical climate of the firm and many aspects of job satisfaction. Further, HAGHANI & RAFII (2013) discovered a significant and significant beneficial link between the social atmosphere and the point to which the healthcare caregivers were happier at work. Amongst variables that make up a section, the operating mobility, the wage level, and the kind of responsibilities that are assigned all have a significant effect on work fulfillment.

Additionally, Schwepker, (2001) Results recommend that salesmen's impression of a decent moral milieu is decidedly associated with the joy they get from their employment and the obligation they have in formal leadership roles. Lastly, the ethical climate and moral

authority were decidedly connected with job satisfaction. The various relapse examinations strategy additionally affirmed that the ethical climate, political conduct, and moral initiative productively had huge prescient capacity in regards to job satisfaction. Naiyananont & Smuthranond, (2017).

Ethical Climate	Job Satisfaction						
	Working Condition	Supervisor	Pay	Job Itself	Organization as a whole	Promotion	Overall
Self Interest	.517* (0.000)	.447* (0.000)	.331* (0.000)	.315* (0.000)	.473* (0.000)	.440* (0.000)	.565* (0.000)
Organization	.290* (0.000)	.301* (0.000)	.485* (0.000)	.428* (0.000)	.493* (0.000)	.458* (0.000)	.551* (0.000)
Profit Efficiency	.384* (0.000)	.385* (0.000)	.398* (0.000)	.451* (0.000)	.534* (0.000)	.489* (0.000)	.591* (0.000)
Team Interest	.362* (0.000)	.335* (0.000)	.397* (0.000)	.477* (0.000)	.551* (0.000)	.548* (0.000)	.597* (0.000)
Social Responsibility	.306* (0.000)	.429* (0.000)	.402* (0.000)	.351* (0.000)	.446* (0.000)	.457* (0.000)	.537* (0.000)
Personal Morality	.471* (0.000)	.384* (0.000)	.430* (0.000)	.522* (0.000)	.556* (0.000)	.475* (0.000)	.635* (0.000)
Rules	.385* (0.000)	.373* (0.000)	.442* (0.000)	.492* (0.000)	.564* (0.000)	.496* (0.000)	.617* (0.000)
Professional Codes	.496* (0.000)	.487* (0.000)	.530* (0.000)	.555* (0.000)	.662* (0.000)	.617* (0.000)	.750* (0.000)
Overall							

Table 5: Significance of the Relationship between the Ethical Climate and Job Satisfaction

E. The extent of Influence of Predictor Variables on Job Satisfaction

The amount of the impact that various predictor factors have on the employees' commitment experienced by law enforcement personnel in Agusan del Sur may be shown in Table 6. It is possible to derive these from the findings that the predictor variables Transformational Leadership and Ethical Climate has a combined percentage result of with an F ratio of 142.987 with p-value of .000, which is < 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, job satisfaction may be significantly improved by combining the positive benefits of strategic leadership with an organizational trust in the workplace.

Further, police officers in Agusan del Sur have some degree of Job Satisfaction and the R2 .572 shows that 57.2% of the variance in job satisfaction is contributed by the two independent variables namely, Transformational Leadership and Ethical Climate. Moreover, data show the following t value of the independent variables, namely: Transformational Leadership 2.167 with p= .031, hence, significant (p<0.05); and Ethical Climate, 8.518 with p= .000, hence significant (p<0.05). From the result, Transformational Leadership and Ethical Consideration has a significant influence on Job

Satisfaction. Therefore, the prediction model of the study based on Table 6 is:

Prediction Equation Model:

$$Y_{JS} = 0.207 + 0.160X_{TL} + 0.628X_{EC}$$

Where: Y_{JS} = Job Satisfaction

X_{TL} = Transformational Leadership

X_{EC} = Ethical Climate

This denotes that every 0.160-unit increase in the level of Transformational Leadership, there is a corresponding 1-unit increase in the level of Job Satisfaction. It also indicates that every 0.628-unit increase in the level of Ethical Climate, there is a corresponding 1-unit increase in the level of Job Satisfaction.

This study is congruent with the studies of Tesfaw, (2014); and Ahmad, Bushra, Naveed & U, (2011); and Boamah, Clarke, Laschinger & Wong, (2018); and Okpara & Wynn, (2008); and HAGHANI & RAFII (2013); and Schwepker, (2001); and Naiyananont & Smuthranond, (2017). That transformational leadership and ethical climate influences the job satisfaction.

Job Satisfaction (Dependent Variables)				
Independent Variables	β (Standardized Coefficients)	B (Unstandardized Coefficients)	t	Sig.
Constant	.889	.207	4.285	.000
Transformational Leadership (TL)	.159	.160	2.167	.031
Ethical Climate (EC)	.624	.628	8.518	.000
R	.756			
R ²	.572			
F	142.987			
p	.000			

Table 6: The extent of Influence of Predictor Variables on Job Satisfaction

This denotes that every 0.160-unit increase in the level of Transformational Leadership, there is a corresponding 1-unit increase in the level of Job Satisfaction. It also indicates that every 0.628-unit increase in the level of Ethical Climate, there is a corresponding 1-unit increase in the level of Job Satisfaction.

The study is aligned with the study of Tesfaw, (2014) the discoveries demonstrated that a moderate, there is a link that may be characterized as both positive and crucial regarding idealized influence (in general) and supervisory support. Result of the study is also parallel with the statement of Ahmad, Bushra, Naveed & U, (2011). The findings of the study concluded that transformational leadership positively affects job satisfaction and organizational commitment of employees. Subsequently, it was shown that effective leaders had a significant and favorable effect on work resilience, which in product helps job happiness; increased employee content was associated with fewer unfavorable occurrences (Boamah, Clarke, Laschinger & Wong, 2018).

Furthermore, the result of the study was supported by the statement of Okpara & Wynn, (2008). There was a relate between the ethical climate of the firm and many aspects of job satisfaction. Additionally, there was a strong relation between ethical climate types and organizational commitment. This suggests that a positive ethical climate in the workplace would stimulate job satisfaction. Also, HAGHANI & RAFII (2013) discovered a significant and significant beneficial link between the social atmosphere and the degree to which the medical caregivers were satisfied with their jobs. From among variables that make up a section, the functioning mobility, the wage level, and the kind of responsibilities that are assigned all have a significant association with job pleasure.

Additionally, Schwepker, (2001) Results recommend that salesmen's impression of a work happiness and supervisory duties are inextricably linked to the presence of a healthy virtuous atmosphere. Lastly, the ethical climate and moral authority were decidedly connected with job satisfaction. The various relapse examinations strategy additionally affirmed that the ethical climate, political conduct, and moral initiative productively had huge prescient capacity in regards to job satisfaction. Naiyananont & Smuthranond, (2017)

IV. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The researcher came to the following important conclusion based on the study's findings. The level of transformational leadership is very high, the ethical climate also very high and still, the job satisfaction is very high. The results also disclose that transformational leadership and ethical climate has significant relationship to job satisfaction. Actually, the two variables are the predictors and has influence job satisfaction. The job satisfaction of police officers with indices motivation, appreciation, belongingness, and sense of responsibility has something to do with transformational leadership and ethical climate.

Overall, the study believes with (Frederick Herzberg, 1959) built a two-dimensional model of the factors that influence people's attitudes toward work. He stated when a superior input motivation to a certain organization it will have a long-term effect on their job satisfaction. It also supported by (Diener & Morrison, 2011), When people are more dependent on their culture and surroundings, national contentment predicts life fulfillment more accurately. (Charland, 1998), conclude that appreciation, which is a major theoretical term in many current approaches to competence, contains significant emotive components that are rarely recognized or acknowledged. And also, the level of crime in a community has the greatest impact on a police officer's sense of responsibility as a result of their proactive behavior. (Jackson & Wade, 2005) therefore, a police officer who have job satisfaction can perform properly and effectively by giving service to the people, a highly transformational leadership can help the organization by innovating and inspiring their subordinate to be more reactive in the performance of their duty and those police officers that belong to the organization must exercise the ethical climate to promote orderly and none toxic working environment that cannot affect in their work.

In light of the aforementioned findings and the study's conclusion, the researcher has made the following recommendations:

According to the findings of the study, commissioned officers in the Agusan del Sur Provincial Police Office maintained a very high level of job satisfaction while fulfilling the PNP's goals via increasing transformational leadership. Also, the very high level of ethical climate among

non-commissioned officers maintained very high, in terms of Self Interest the researcher highly recommend that the non-commissioned police officers need to increase their selfless service to the people and consider also their welfare by doing active activities on their off duty to boost physical and mental aspect, by doing so it can help them to be productive and energize for their upcoming duties.

For the PNP, the researcher highly suggests that conducting trainings and seminars can increased the potential of the commissioned officer to lead their subordinate with a confident and equipped guidelines to guide the organization improvements and undeniably service for the community in order for their subordinate's manifestation of job satisfaction. For the non-commissioned police officers, it can be a big help for them to enhance active listening towards instructions and guidelines of their commissioned officers in effective performance of their duty. Also, self-care and active physical activities in increasing the energy and excluding negative impact for their selves.

Finally, it is recommended, for future researches, that other variables can be studied to determine other factors that promote job satisfaction among police officers.

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